

EMPIRICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF DEVELOPING LANGUAGE SKILLS THROUGH INTERACTIVE DIGITAL PLATFORMS (DUOLINGO, QUIZLET, KAHOOT) IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses the methodology and empirical evaluation of the effectiveness of developing language skills through interactive digital platforms (Duolingo, Quizlet, Kahoot) in English language teaching.

Keywords: English language, digital platforms, Duolingo, Quizlet, Kahoot, methodology, empirical evaluation.

ЭМПИРИЧЕСКАЯ ОЦЕНКА МЕТОДОЛОГИИ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЯЗЫКОВЫХ НАВЫКОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПЛАТФОРМ (DUOLINGO, QUIZLET, KAHOOT) В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются методология и эмпирическая оценка эффективности развития языковых навыков с помощью интерактивных цифровых платформ (Duolingo, Quizlet, Kahoot) в преподавании английского языка.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, цифровые платформы, Duolingo, Quizlet, Kahoot, методология, эмпирическая оценка.

Modern education is in a constant process of change and improvement under the influence of information technologies. One such technology is the use of interactive platforms that make learning more engaging and motivating for students.

The main problem in education is the low level of students' motivation to learn foreign languages, particularly English. Many schoolchildren struggle to learn, see no point in learning a foreign language, and quickly lose interest in the lessons.

Standard teaching methods sometimes cannot generate interest in students, which is why it is important to use new approaches to learning to increase motivation and the effectiveness of material assimilation.

Interactive platforms for learning foreign languages in primary school provide students with the opportunity to practice language skills in an interactive format.

Examples of platforms and online simulators:

1. Duolingo is one of the most popular platforms for learning foreign languages. Duolingo offers students interactive exercises, games, tests, and lessons that help develop grammar, listening, and pronunciation skills.

2. Babbel is another popular platform offering training courses in various foreign languages. Babbel is designed to allow students to practice language in real situations, such as travel, work, and communication.

3. Rosetta Stone is a well-known platform with a unique approach to language learning. Rosetta Stone is based on the immersion method, offering students learning in the language they are learning without using translation.

4. Memrise - an online simulator for memorizing words and phrases in foreign languages. Memrise uses the repetition method and associations to help students memorize new vocabulary.

5. Lingodeer is an interactive language learning application, especially popular among beginner students. Lingodeer offers a game-based learning approach, making the process more engaging.

Examples of online games:

1. Wordwall is an online platform for creating interactive games on various topics, including foreign languages. Teachers can create games that help students practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation.

2. Quizlet is a popular foreign language application that offers students a series of games and tasks for language skills training. Quizlet also allows you to create your own card sets and learn together with friends.

3. SpeakingPal - an application for learning pronunciation and colloquial speech in foreign languages. SpeakingPal offers students have the opportunity to communicate with a virtual interlocutor and receive feedback about their pronunciation.

Interactive platforms for teachers:

1. Kahoot allows you to create interactive tests and quizzes that can be used both in class and for independent learning. The teacher can ask questions in English, add pictures and videos, and allow students to compete with each other in real time.

2. EdPuzzle - allows the teacher to create video lessons with questions and tasks that students can complete directly while watching the video. This is a great way not only to improve understanding but also to test students' knowledge.

3. Genially. It offers ample opportunities for creating interactive games that can be used in the learning process. These games allow students to learn in game form, making the learning process more engaging and engaging. First stands determine the learning objective and choose the appropriate game format.

Then, you need to create interactive elements, add animations and sound effects to create an engaging gaming environment. After that, the game can be posted and shared with students.

Advantages of interactive platforms:

long-term storage of educational materials in the service cloud);

analysis and control of the obtained data;

Availability of templates for creating games of varying complexity and completeness;

visual gamification;

flexibility and mobility (access to platforms is possible from any devices).

An example of how interactive platforms can be utilized in English language lessons is illustrated by the use of the Genially platform. The Genially service can create presentations, games, infographics, interactive posters, and quests. The Genially service can make presentations, games, infographics, interactive posters, and quests.

Educational games not only improved students' motivation to learn a foreign language, but also encouraged active engagement with the material, developed their skills and abilities,

and provided a sense of satisfaction from achieving in-game goals. This helped them assimilate new material more effectively and enhance their language skills.

Thus, the use of interactive platforms for creating educational games can be an effective way to enhance students' motivation to learn English. Such games make learning more engaging and interesting, which contributes to more effective assimilation of the material. It is important to further research and develop such approaches to teaching using modern information technologies in order to achieve better results in education.

Below are some of them:

Blended approach is a mixed learning format that combines traditional and distance learning methods. Students master part of the material independently on online platforms, and then reinforce their knowledge during face-to-face classes.

Virtual Reality (VR) is the creation of an environment for immersing students in an English-speaking setting, offering the opportunity for virtual tours to countries where the target language is spoken, and providing realistic situational language learning.

Gamification is the application of game elements and mechanics in the learning process to motivate and engage students. Creating game tasks and competitions, the purpose of which is to teach English. (Kahoot, Learning apps, Wordwall, Duolingo, Quizlet, Memrise, Rosetta Stone, Hello Talk, etc.).

Mobile applications and online platforms - Kahoot, Learning apps, Wordwall, Duolingo, Quizlet, Memrise, Rosetta Stone, Hello Talk.

Audio and video materials - using audio and video lessons, audiobooks, films, and TV series in English to develop listening comprehension skills. Creating your own video and audio recordings to practice pronunciation and speaking.

Cloud technologies - a service through which users receive specific computing resources via the network, such as RAM, network connections, and disk space for solving various tasks.

Interactive whiteboards and devices, mobile devices and tablets - they excel at "bringing lessons to life", enhancing presentations at events, etc. Learning becomes creative and engaging, as the internal motivation for learning increases.

In conclusion, the use of digital platforms in English language teaching proves to be an effective modern educational methodology. The purposeful and systematic integration of these tools into educational programs plays a crucial role in developing students' language skills. In the future, it is advisable to conduct more extensive empirical research in this field, as well as to develop methodological recommendations for other languages.

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